

D7.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan, including an overview of planned training activities

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Abstract:	<i>This communication and dissemination plan is a public deliverable from the BatCAT consortium, meant to inform the general public on our plans. It includes an overview over the planned training activities. This is version no. 2 of deliverable D7.1, produced for milestone 10.</i>
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1 Purpose of the document

BatCAT is the project that will realize the BATTERY 2030+ manufacturability programme from 2024 to 2028, addressing battery cell manufacturing innovation for LIB and Na-ion cells as well as redox-flow batteries, thus covering portable and stationary applications.

The communication and dissemination plan provides the framework of all activities for informing and educating internal and external stakeholders about the project. The awareness about the project and knowledge about the project results will lead to a higher degree of exploitation.

This document is a deliverable by Month 6 of the project.

The relevant communication channels are discussed with respect to the target stakeholders and content for communication.

The target audiences for communication efforts are identified as the general public, academia, industry and policy makers. For each of those parties relevant communication channels have been identified, to meet their specific needs and preferences for receiving information about the BatCAT project.

2 Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Stakeholder engagement, training

The actions in these plans will maximize the impact and exploitation of the project. The BatCAT dissemination and communication activities target four specific stakeholder groups, in line with the quadruple helix approach:

The general public

Relevant stakeholders from the general public are university and high school students who can be encouraged to choose a career path in the battery manufacturing sector by being informed about the current developments and opportunities. This is also a good opportunity particularly regarding the gender dimension.

Academic institutions

Academic institutions and researchers working on similar projects need to be made aware of the BatCAT project in order to create areas for collaboration and knowledge transfer.

Industry

As the BatCAT project is specific to the manufacturing of batteries, the awareness of the battery manufacturing industry is crucial for a good exploitation of the results of the project as well as establishing collaborations between industry partners and

Policymakers

The BatCAT project has received funding by the EU and the Battery 2030+, it is therefore in their interest to be informed about the progress of the project. This is to strengthen the project's societal impact.

2.1.1 Analysis of dissemination tools for the different stake holders

Activities are adapted to each stakeholder group to maximize visibility and support specific exploitation. For the scientific community, the main dissemination activities are conferences and scientific papers. For the industry, project results will be presented at industrial fairs and industrial magazines with a focus on how to use the project results in an industrial environment. Policymakers will be informed about the standardization potential of digitalized battery testing using a federated data organization. Entertaining short stories, infographics, and video clips will be used to explain the benefits of digital technologies to citizens, explaining how job opportunities will be created and waste reduced. A good communication strategy is key to disseminating the project's outcome to all relevant stakeholders, maximizing its impact on heterogeneous communities.

The following table analyses the relevance of the different dissemination tools for the different stakeholders.

Dissemination Tool / Stakeholder	General public	Academic institutions	Industry	Policymakers
Scientific publications and conferences	Low	High	High	Medium
Project website	High	Medium	Medium	Low
Social Media: LinkedIn	High	Low	Medium	Low
News posts (also social media like LinkedIn)	Medium	Medium	High	Low
Hackathon	Medium	High	Medium	Low
Training events (together with consortial meetings)	Medium	High	Medium	Low
Webinars	Medium	High	Medium	Low

2.2 Scientific publications and conferences

Project results will be published in the scientific literature, dedicated journals, and magazines relevant to the stakeholders of BatCAT, both in the academia and for industrial practitioners. All scientific publications will be openly accessible on Zenodo.

The list of publications in journals will grow further as the project progresses.

Scientific Journals	BatCAT research area	lead partners	no. of papers	No. already done
International Journal of Thermophysics	Multiscale modelling	RPTU	2	2
Journal of Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics	Transport process simulations	RPTU	1	1
Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data	Modelling of thermophysical properties of electrolyte solvents	RPTU	1	1
Journal of Physical Chemistry C	Molecular simulation of wetting and adsorption in mixture systems	RPTU	1	1
Fluid Phase Equilibria	Multiscale modelling of polar interactions for solvents	RPTU	1	1
Nature communications	Entropy scaling for diffusion coefficients in fluid mixtures	RPTU	1	1
Materials & Design	Materials design for electrodes (LIBs)	LOYOLA	1	
Journal of Power Sources	Simulation of manufacturing process	LOYOLA	1	
Journal of the Electrochemical Society	Simulation of manufacturing process	LOYOLA	1	
International Journal of Forecasting	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU	1	
IEEE Access	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU	1	
Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU	1	
Journal of Computational Physics	Modelling of Redox flow batteries	NMBU/SI MULA/Va nevo/UK RI	2	
ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces	Multiscale modelling of solid electrolyte interfaces (SEI)	IFPEN	1	
Computers in Industry	Battery Digital Twin Semantics and Applications	GCL	1	
IEEE Access	Ontology Learning, Schema Alignment, Mapping, Cellular Neural Network (CeNN) ML Predictor	AAU, NMBU	1-2	-

IEEE Open (Data Descriptions, Industrial Electronics)	Qualitative Logical Reasoning, Real-time Functionality, Manufacturing Process	AAU, NMBU	1-2	-
Journal of Chemical Physics	Combining multi-criteria optimization of molecular models with machine learning	HSKL	1	
Journal of Catalysis	The necessity of dynamic workflow managers for advancing self-driving labs and optimisers, to be submitted	DTU	1	
IEEE Access	Beyond Deep Learning: Cellular Neural Networks (CeNNs) as a Paradigm Shift for Ultrafast, Robust, Uncertainty-Aware, and Resource-Efficient Multivariate Time-Series Forecasting	AAU	1	

List of published publications:

- S. Stephan et al.: Mass transfer at vapor-liquid interfaces of H₂O + CO₂ mixtures studied by molecular dynamics simulation, J. Non-Equilib. Thermodyn. 49 (2024) 441-461.
- J. Staubach et al.: Helmholtz energy models for dipole interactions: Review and comprehensive Assessment, Fluid Ph. Equilib. 585 (2024) 114168.
- H. Rennis et al.: Characteristic Curves of Polar Fluids: (I) The Two-Center Lennard–Jones Plus Dipole Fluid, Int. J. Thermophys. 45-6 (2024) 73.
- H. Rennis et al.: Characteristic Curves of Polar Fluids: (II) The Two-Center Lennard–Jones Plus Quadrupole Fluid, Int. J. Thermophys. 45 (2024) 77.
- S. Schmitt et al.: Measurements and Equation of State Modeling of the Density of Five 1-Alcohols (C₆-C₁₀) at Pressures up to 120 Mpa, J.Chem. Eng. Data 69-9 (2024) 2967-2983.
- S. Schmitt et al.: Entropy scaling for diffusion coefficients in fluid mixtures, Nat. Commun. 16 (2025) 2611.
- D. Fertig et al.: Molecular Dynamics Study of Adsorption and Wetting of Mixtures of Simple Fluids on Planar Walls, J. Phys. Chem. C 128-27 (2024) 11340-11354.

Conferences targeted for collaborative contributions from BatCAT:

Conference	BatCAT research area	partners	no. of papers planned	No of finished conferences
STAMS 2025	Modelling of Manufacturing process (LIBs)	LOYOLA, POLITO	1	
Particles 2025	Modelling of Manufacturing process (LIBs)	Loyola	1	
Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AAAI)	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU	1	
European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI)	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU, AAU	1	
Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD)	Decision Support / Surrogate model/ Time Series	NMBU	1	

European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI)	Actionable Modelling Logical Reasoning.	AAU, NMBU	1-2	
IEEE Conference on Artificial Intelligence	Logical Reasoning under Uncertainty, ASP, Real-time Functionality	AAU, NMBU	1-2	
Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD)	Ontology Learning, Schema Alignment	AAU, NMBU	1	
IEEE Circuits and Systems Society (IEEE CASS) Conference	Decision Support/ ML Models	AAU, NMBU	1	
ModVal 2025 - 21st Symposium on Modeling and Validation of Electrochemical Energy Technologies in Karlsruhe, Germany	Comparative analysis of ethylene carbonate decomposition in Li ₂ CO ₃ and Na ₂ CO ₃ -based solid electrolyte interphases (oral presentation)	IFPEN	1	1
249th ECS (The Electrochemical Society) Meeting May 24-28, 2026 – Seattle, WA, US		SIMULA	-	
78th ICE (International Society of Electrochemistry) annual meeting 2027 5-10 September, Glasgow, UK		SIMULA	-	
253rd ECS Meeting May 21-25, 2028 – Gothenburg, Sweden		SIMULA	-	
International Conference on Applied Mathematics & Computer Science (ICAMCS), Venice, Italy, 2024	Combining Autoencoder and Cellular Neural Networks for Enhanced Direct Multi-Step Forecasting of Short and Long-Term Multivariate Time Series in Battery Health Monitoring: A Preliminary Feasibility Analysis (Paper and Talk)	AAU	1	1
AutSys 2024, Mallorca (Conference), Spain. 25th - 30th October, 2024	Enhancing Long-Term Battery Health Multivariate Time-Series Prediction Monitoring: A Comparative Study of Neural Networks, Autoencoders, and Transformer Models (Talk)	AAU	-	1

Batteries Event 2025, Lyon, 4-6Nov. 2025	Impact of manufacturing parameters on battery cell behaviour.	IFPEN	1	
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KPIs: By end of project, there are ≥ 18 publications attributed to BatCAT in journals with an impact factor ≥ 2.0 , and there are ≥ 36 publications attributed to BatCAT overall (including all journals and conference proceedings). Additionally, emerging innovative publication outlets such as *ing.grid* will be considered for data-oriented formats such as peer-reviewed data publications (in addition to publishing in the traditional formats, not replacing it).

Inevitably not all conferences pertinent to the topics as covered within the BatCAT programme have been announced and publicised, therefore we anticipate that numerous other conferences will also be of interest to all partners in due course. The conferences that will be targeted are likely to be similar in topic to those listed above.

2.2.1 Workshops and other dissemination similar to conferences

This section lists the workshops and other dissemination similar to conferences including conferences where there are only abstracts but no papers

- Battery2030+ events (& related projects such as BIG-MAP)
 - Grindelwald European Battery Data Space Workshop 2024 (short presentation only)
 - Battery2030+ Conference, Grenoble, 2024 (presentation and abstract only, no paper); contributors: Whole consortium
 - Oslo Battery Workshop, 2024 (presentation and abstract only, no paper); contributors: Whole consortium
 - Battery2030+ roadmap workshop 19.03.2025 (DTU, NMBU)
 - We will regularly participate in Battery2030+ events throughout the project runtime.
- CAPE-OPEN Annual Meeting 2024; contributors: NMBU
 - [Moving from FAIR data principles to XAIR](#), CAPE-OPEN Annual Meeting, Berlin, 8 October 2024
- 22nd Symposium on Thermophysical Properties Modelling and prediction of thermophysical properties (presentations and abstracts only, no paper); contributor: RPTU
- Open Innovation Platform Conference 2024, Kaiserslautern (presentation and abstract only, no paper); contributors: ITWM, HSKL, LIST, NMBU, RPTU, UKRI
- Thermodynamik-Kolloquium (annually, planned to contribute three times; presentation and abstract only, no paper); contributors: RPTU, HSKL
- Joint Ontology Workshops (JOWO, annually, planned to contribute twice; as a result, there will be two papers); contributors: AAU, ITWM, LIST, NMBU, UKRI
- DTE-AICOMAS 2025, Paris; contributors: NMBU, SIMULA, UKRI, VANEVO.
 - [Digital twin and dataspace architecture for vanadium redox-flow batteries in view of requirements for the digital materials and product passport](#), *Artificial Intelligence and Computational Methods in Applied Science and III. IACM Digital Twins in Engineering Conference* (DTE-AICOMAS 2025), Paris, 21 February 2025

- + another talk by Sudeepika Liyanapathirana (NMBU)
- Thermodynamics 2027 (presentation and abstract only, no paper): HSKL, ITWM, NMBU, RPTU, UKRI
- MolMod Workshop 2026: RPTU, HSKL, NMBU
- European Symposium on Applied Thermodynamics 2026 (presentation and abstract only, no paper): HSKL, LOYOLA, NMBU, RPTU, UKRI
- ICIAM 2027 (presentation and abstract only, no paper): ITWM, NMBU, RPTU, SIMULA, UKRI
- eSENCE workshop (at least once): DTU, NMBU
- SeMatS 2024: International Workshop on Semantic Materials Science (presentation plus paper): GCL, HSKL, ITWM, LIST, NMBU, RPTU, SIMULA, UKRI
 - M. T. Horsch, D. Romanov, E. Valseth, S. Belouettar, L. E. Córdova López, J. Glutting, M. A. Janssen, P. Klein, A. Linhart, M. A. Seaton, E. D. Sødahl, N. Vizcaino, S. Werth, S. Stephan, I. T. Todorov, S. Chiacchiera & F. Al Machot (2024). [Battery manufacturing knowledge infrastructure requirements for multicriteria optimization based decision support in design of simulation](#). In A. Valdestilhas *et al.* (editors), *Proceedings of the First International Workshop on Semantic Materials Science*: 5. CEUR-WS, Aachen.
 - Presentation: [Battery manufacturing knowledge infrastructure requirements for multicriteria optimization based decision support in design of simulation](#), *International Workshop on Semantic Materials Science (SeMatS)*, Amsterdam, 17 September 2024
- DAO-XAI 2024: International Workshop on Data meets Applied Ontologies in Explainable AI (presentation plus paper): NMBU, RPTU, UKRI
 - M. T. Horsch, S. Chiacchiera, I. T. Todorov, A. T. Correia, A. Dey, N. A. Konchakova, S. Scholze, S. Stephan, K. Tøndel, A. Sarkar, M. H. Karray, F. Al Machot & B. Schembera (2024). [Exploration of core concepts required for mid- and domain-level ontology development to facilitate explainable-AI-readiness of data and models](#). In R. Confalonieri *et al.* (editors), *Data meets Ontologies in Explainable AI 2024*: 5. CEUR-WS, Aachen.
 - Presentation: [Exploration of core concepts required for mid- and domain-level ontology development to facilitate explainable-AI-readiness of data and models](#), *IV. International Workshop on Data meets Applied Ontologies in Explainable AI (DAO-XAI)*, Santiago de Compostela, 19 October 2024
- MSE2026: Materials Science and Engineering Congress in Germany. Materials science engineering including batteries. Abstracts and posters: GCL
- DCLXVI 2024 Workshop; see papers below. These were also presented as talks.
 - e.g., [Scope of physics-based simulation artefacts](#), *International Workshop on Designing the Conceptual Landscape for a XAIR Validation Infrastructure (DCLXVI)*, Kaiserslautern, 11 December 2024
- AABC Europe (presentation and abstract only, no paper); contributors: CPI, BIREX
- Battery Show Europe; contributors: CPI, BIREX
- EuroMat 2025 (presentation and abstract only, no paper): 18th European Congress and Exhibition on Advanced Materials and Processes. Advanced materials and processes including batteries. Abstracts and posters: GCL
- IndTech2025 (presentation and abstract only, no paper): Conference on industrial technologies. Industrial technologies including ontologies. Abstracts: GCL.

- EMMC 2025 International Workshop (poster and abstract only, no paper): International workshop on materials modelling and digitalisation. Contributors: NMBU, UKRI, GCL
- EU Unified Battery Data Landscape MOOC within Battery 2030+: DTU
- Organization of a battery modelling summer school – 01/09/2025-05/09/2025 at DTU
- Workshop of DTU and FULLMAP on the alignment of DMP and data infrastructure with FULLMAP 03.2025
- Joint Ontology Workshops (JOWO) - Schema Alignment and Mapping - AAU, ITWM, LIST, NMBU, UKRI
- Digital Age Research Center (D!ARC) -University Klagenfurt, 26th November 2024, V.1.0.7 - Enhancing Battery Health Monitoring in Battery Assembly Digital Twin (BATCAT) (Talk) - AAU

2.2.2 Project website

The project website (www.batcat.info) will continue to grow throughout the progress of the project. This improves the access of the general public as well as policy makers to information about the project.

KPI: 1-2 items per month

2.2.3 News posts. (Website and LinkedIn)

Planned topics for news posts include: General information on battery manufacturing digitalization; simulation methodology; infographics; references to upcoming publications; summary of publications; attendance at conferences and meetings; event promotion.

KPI: two posts per month.

BatCAT will use LinkedIn to spread information about the project. The channel can also help promote other work from similar projects and organizations that may be of interest to our audience, such as those involved within the Battery2030+ collaboration.

3 Training activities and training programme organization

BatCAT disseminates training material and organizes training events, providing background knowledge on key topics and documentation material of newly developed tools to the community. In addition to webinars and other digitized training material, two internal and three openly advertised training events will be held in person, collocated with the consortial meetings. The digitized training materials are transferred into the public domain as OER. Joint training activities are organized with BATTERY 2030+ (incl. BIG-MAP, SENSIBAT), DigiPass CSA, and EMMC (and related projects). A mid-term strategy for uptake of content in university and further education is developed, with particular regard to the gender dimension.

3.1 MOOCs Massive Open Online Courses

MOOCs are massive open online course that are open and accessible to everyone online. The European Multiple MOOC Aggregator EMMA is an online platform that hosts a variety of MOOCs on different

subjects. MOOCs are addressed at a wider audience, in contrast to an audience with specialist knowledge.

One MOOC will be on the manufacturing process of different cell types. MOOC participants will learn about common cell chemistries, how they are built and what their advantages and disadvantages are. Based on this knowledge, the MOOC participants will first learn about the most common manufacturing practices as well as new and currently experimental manufacturing methods. Furthermore, they will learn about the current challenges with battery manufacturing focusing on new battery technologies and Europe as a location for battery manufacturing.

Another MOOC will be on the development of digital twins, with battery manufacturing processes as a use case examples. The participants will first learn about the basic concepts of digital twins, possible applications and where they are useful as well as which types of digital twins there are. They will learn about sensor integration and IoT and the importance of data collection. Next, the course demonstrates how modelling and simulation techniques create a virtual representation of reality and incorporate real time data.

Published MOOCs:

- EU Unified Battery Data Landscape MOOC within Battery 2030+

3.2 Joint Digitalization Hackathon on energy storage solutions

BatCAT will organize a joint digitalization hackathon together with BATTwin and/or DigiPass CSA.

The Digitization Hackathon on Energy Storage Innovations is an event where engineers, developers, data scientists, and energy experts collaborate to develop innovative solutions for energy storage digitalization.

Kickoff and Team Formation:

Participants form teams based on shared interests.

Ideation and Development:

Teams brainstorm and select projects aimed at improving energy storage efficiency, capacity, and sustainability. Using digital solutions like data analytics, AI, and IoT, they work intensively on developing prototypes and applications, with guidance from mentors.

Workshops and Progress Check-ins:

Participants attend workshops on relevant technologies and regularly update organizers on their progress.

Final Presentations:

Teams present their projects to a panel, focusing on the problem addressed, their solution, and its potential impact. Panels evaluate the projects based on innovation, feasibility, and impact, and provide feedback.

Networking:

The event concludes with networking opportunities and closing remarks.

3.3 Consortial Meeting Training Sessions

Over the duration of the BatCAT project there will be five consortial meetings, where the partners meet in person.

The training events which are part of the consortial meetings of M21, M30 and M39 will be open to the public.

3.3.1 M3 Cell manufacturing challenges

The focus of the first consortial meeting was on getting familiar with similar research projects as well as introducing specific partners and their resources specific to the BatCAT project. This

In March 24 the following training sessions were held as integral part of the consortial meeting.

- “RFB manufacturing challenges” An introduction to the production challenges in redox flow batteries.
- “SALAMANDER” The Salamander project was presented which is a EU-funded project researching smart sensors and self-healing functionalities for Li-ion batteries.
- “Challenges and perspectives of battery digital twin development” by Ferry Kienberger
- “LinkAhead” A platform for collaborative data management was presented.
- OpenSemanticLab and BIG-MAP Notebook – Battery related data organization including metadata necessary to describe cell chemistries as well as cycling protocols.

3.3.2 M12 MCO

The manufacturing of batteries has different criteria that are desirable, but cannot be optimised at the same time and might be contrary to each other. In addition to this immediate use in process and product design, multicriteria optimization will in BatCAT also be applied to model parameterization, design of experiment, and design of simulation. This requires the whole consortium to understand and engage with the method. The training sessions that are planned so far are listed before. They are categorised by confirmed speakers, tentative speakers and proposed speakers.

The following training programs were held in M12:

- ITWM as lead of T5.2 “Multicriteria optimization” present MCO methodologies and how they will be integrated into the BatCAT architecture and used for the digital twin development.
- DCLXVI 2024 International Workshop: Designing the Conceptual Landscape for a XAIR Validation Infrastructure. More information here: <https://batcat.info/dclxvi/>

3.3.3 M21 Online Characterization

- An open workshop on online characterization is held.

3.3.4 M30 BatCAT DT platform MVP

The aim of the BatCAT project is the development of digital twins in the battery cell manufacturing process. Therefore, this meeting will deal with the minimum viable product (MVP) of the digital twin.

- An open training session is held on digital twin technologies, showing how the technology is applied within the BatCAT project.

- RPTU presents the MVP status shown for actionable modelling.
- AAU presents the qualitative logical reasoning module and how its building blocks interact within the real-time environment of a manufacturing process.
- LIST presents how the real-time functionality was implemented.
- VANEVO presents how the functional requirements from industrial stakeholders were communicated to the work packages to lead to the development results matching the industry requirements.

All of the above is primarily directed at external stakeholders who want to learn about our technology.

3.3.5 M39 Final validated BatCAT DT platform

The last training event will be held when the digital twin has been developed and a validation process was carried out.

- An open training event will be held on the developed digital twin technology and the BatCAT project outcomes.
- DTU presents how human-digital interactions function within the digital twin technology and how experiments are guided through the IIDSS for an optimal gain of information balanced against the resources spend.
- HSKL presents how the models have been tested for transferability between different chemistries and scales and the two use cases.
- CPI presents how the digital twin has improved the manufacturing performance in a real world environment.

All of the above is primarily directed at external stakeholders who want to learn about our technology.

4 Summary with selected key performance indicators

Dissemination Tool	Activity /	Due Date or Regularity or KPIs
Scientific publications and conferences	The activity's due dates and regularity as well as the responsibility is described in detail in the section "Scientific publications and conferences"	
Project website	Minimum of 1-2 News item	Monthly
Social Media: LinkedIn	Social media post about the progress of the project, interesting battery related news, facts, short storeys	1-2 monthly posts
Hackathon	A hackathon on energy storage manufacturing digitalization is carried out with one or both of the following partners: BATTwin, DigiPass	M20-M26 (might still change, no hard dead line)

MOOCs	MOOCs are developed to be published under the EU platform for MOOCs	2 throughout the projects runtime
M12 training event	Internal training events	
M21 training event	Open workshop on online characterisation within digitized manufacturing	≥ 10 external participants ≥ 4 institutions
M30 training event	Open training on digital twin technology	≥ 20 external participants ≥ 8 institutions
M39 training event	Open training event on the overall technology	≥ 50 external participants ≥ 20 institutions
BatCAT knowledge base node operated by POLITO	≥ 10000 data points for phenomenological properties from simulation are made openly accessible	M27